

Appendix C - List of extracted unique SOBM concepts

Index	Concept	Count
1	sustainable business model	61
2	circular economy	54
3	circular business model	40
4	business model for sustainability	15
5	product-service system	10
6	sustainable business model innovation	9
7	sharing economy	8
8	circular business model innovation	6
9	eco-innovation	4
10	regenerative business models	3
11	social enterprise	3
12	sustainability-oriented business models	3
13	b corp	4
14	hybrid organizations	3
15	green business model	3
16	circular economy business model	3
17	circular startup	3
18	sharing economy business model	3
19	sustainable entrepreneurship	2
20	social business model	2
21	circular bioeconomy	2
22	business model innovation for sustainability	2
23	digital-sustainable business models	2
24	servitization-based business models	2
25	circular economy engagement	2
26	truly sustainable business models	1
27	strategic agility	1
28	mimetic sustainable business model	1
29	entrepreneurial sustainable business model	1
30	low-carbon business models	1
31	institutional confluence	1
32	stakeholder perceived value creation	1
33	economically-oriented sbm	1
34	sustainable production	1
35	technology-oriented sustainable business models	1
36	organization-oriented sustainable business model	1

Top 5 SOBM concepts (count ≥ 10)

37	social-oriented sustainable business models	1
38	5hm	1
39	tri-profit	1
40	business models for sustainable development	1
41	socially sustainable organizations	1
42	usage-oriented pss	1
43	product-oriented pss	1
44	socially-oriented sbm	1
45	results-oriented pss	1
46	collaborative business models	1
47	sustainable pss	1
48	social innovation	1
49	environmentally-oriented sbm	1
50	circular use-based cbm	1
51	circular input-based cbm	1
52	circular innovation	1
53	green economy	1
54	sustainable international business model innovation	1
55	circular oriented innovation	1
56	servitized business models	1
57	environmentally sustainable organizations	1
58	circular entrepreneurial ecosystem	1
59	circular economy-based business model	1
60	industrial symbiosis business model	1
61	industrial symbiosis	1
62	bioeconomy	1
63	associative sustainable business model	1
64	servicizing business model	1
65	circular ecosystem	1
66	doughnut economics	1
67	blue economy	1
68	performance economy	1
69	social business	1
70	sustainable enterprise	1
71	hybrid company	1
72	social entrepreneurship	1
73	circular economy oriented business model	1
74	circular business model	1
75	circular business model framework	1

76	business model innovation for circular business models	1
77	more sustainable business model	1
78	open business model	1
79	sustainable open business model	1
80	circular output-based cbm	1
81	base of the pyramid business model	1
82	green and sustainable business model	1
83	sustainability-oriented innovation ecosystem	1
84	cross-sector social partnerships	1
85	closed loop economy	1
86	renewable energy business model	1
87	sustainability-driven hybrid business model	1
88	bmi for circularity	1
89	circular economy model	1
90	sustainable development	1
91	circular economy models adopted by hybrid organizations for sustainable development	1
92	pss business models	1
93	value uncaptured	1
94	sustainable public procurement (spp)	1
95	corporate sustainability	1
96	hybrid organization	1
97	product-service systems' (pss)	1
98	circular economy business models	1
99	extending product value business models (epv bms)	1
100	business models for circular economy	1
101	business models integrating ce principles	1
102	servicized business models	1
103	digital sustainability	1
104	business model innovation	1
105	digital business model innovation	1
106	digital circular business model innovation	1
107	sustainable business	1
108	successful strongly sustainable economy	1
109	strongly sustainable firm	1
110	tri-profit	1
111	strongly sustainable business model	1